

SCIENTIFIC QUESTION ANSWERING USING HYBRID RETRIEVAL AUGMENTED GENERATION

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Abstract

Large language models have strong capabilities for different purposes, such as searching and question-answering [1]. However, they hallucinate on domain-specific tasks. Recent research shows compound systems outperform standalone LLMs [2, 3]. A scientific domain such as Earth observation (EO), used by different fields such as oceanography and environmental science, requires a tailored approach to deal with hallucinations to ensure in-depth answers [4]. This presentation introduces a system for EO that integrates LLM-based conversational search and question-answering by focusing on two components: a) data curation for a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)-based model and b) LLM-based evaluation. For (a), our approach combines multiple data structures connecting different text genres (e.g., scientific and web data). For (b), we test LLM-based evaluation and its alignment with human evaluation.

- **KG-pipeline:** we download publication abstracts from OpenAlex [8], an open index of scholarly works tagged with topics across all scientific domains. We fetch abstracts with topics relevant to EO (e.g., Cosmic Evolution). Also, we download remote sensing and EO data from the DLR geoservice portal¹. Then, we tag both genres using the TaxoTagger. We build a knowledge graph connecting scientific abstracts to artifacts (here, Geoservice data) via the keywords from the tagger.
- **INDEX-pipeline:** We download a search index shard from OpenWebIndex [9] using *owilix* [10, 11], restricted to English data tagged with *science* and *earth* (Curlie tags²). We filter the data with TaxoTagger, excluding those containing keywords below a specified threshold. Finally, we build a Lucene web index using MOSAIC [12].

Figure 1: The two data pipelines: From Data Acquisition and Preprocessing to Knowledge-Graph creation (Top), and index creation (Bottom).

APPROACH

This section outlines our three-stage approach: 1) Data Pipelines, 2) RAG-based LLM, and 3) Evaluation.

1. Data Pipelines. We create an exhaustive dataset of earth observation, including three text genres [5] for two data pipelines. The first pipeline, **KG-pipeline**, (Figure1-top) creates a knowledge graph connecting scientific abstracts to scientific artifacts via keywords. The second pipeline, **INDEX-pipeline** (Figure1-bottom), uses crawled data from the Web, processes it, and generates a searchable index.

To filter and tag the data for the EO domain, we develop an EO Tagger, the TaxoTagger, based on the EO NASA taxonomy [6, 7] (e.g., earth storable), given a text, n keywords are returned with scores between zero and one. Below, we detail each pipeline:

2. RAG-Based LLM. The RAG-based LLM relies on the two pipelines described. When a user queries the LLM, the knowledge graph is queried for the top k results, where each result contains the top hits (nodes), along with their neighboring keywords and nodes. Simultaneously, the Lucene index is also queried for top k hits. These hits are incorporated within the LLM prompt context along with the query.

3. Evaluation For our evaluation, we first curate a set of prompts from domain experts. Due to the absence of reference data, we use Generative Pseudo-Labeling (GPL) [13] to create a weakly labeled dataset for training a response quality classifier. We conduct an automatic evaluation to show the impact of each data pipeline with an ablation study by comparing zero-shot prompting using one of the pipelines, both, or none. Subsequently, domain experts assess the best-performing model on criteria such as faithfulness, relevance, and completeness. Lastly, we compare human evaluations to LLM-based assessments to analyze their alignment.

CONTRIBUTIONS

Our contributions are the following:

- A reservoir of heterogeneous data sources for EO.
- An approach to evaluate the fusion between traditional retrieval (index-based) search with knowledge graph for a scientific domain with a RAG-based model.
- A comparative evaluation approach aligning LLM- and human-based evaluation for a scientific domain.

¹ <https://geoservice.dlr.de> accessed 25.03.2025

² <https://curlie.org/>

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